

Complexes of Ditertiaryphosphine and Arsine Oxides with Metal Ions. Part VIII. Complexes of Uranium(IV) Chloride with 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine/Arsine Oxide and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl) phosphine/Arsine Oxide.

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Uranium(IV) chloride has been found to yield 1 : 1 complexes with the oxides of 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine/arsine and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine/arsine. Infrared spectra of these complexes have been recorded. In view of low values of magnetic susceptibility, extremely low molar conductance and reflectance spectra of these complexes an octahedral stereochemistry for uranium(IV) is suggested.

COMPLEXES of uranium(IV) chloride with a number of oxides of tertiary phosphines¹⁻⁶ and arsines^{2,7,8} have been reported in literature. In the present investigation four complexes of uranium(IV) chloride with the ligands, 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine oxide (EPO), 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl)phosphine oxide (BPO), 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenyl)arsine oxide (EAO) and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenyl)arsine oxide (BAO) have been prepared. The infrared spectra, reflectance spectra, magnetic susceptibility at room temperature and molar conductance of these complexes were recorded in order to compare the coordination behaviour of the four ligands with each other and with other monotertiary phosphine and arsine oxides.

Materials and Methods

The ligands were prepared by the methods already reported in literature^{9,10}. Uranium(IV) acetate was prepared by method reported by Paul and co-workers¹¹.

Preparation of complexes :

Uranium(IV) acetate (1.0 g) was dissolved in a mixture of 10 ml absolute ethanol and 4 ml con-

centrated hydrochloric acid. To this green solution was added the solution of the ditertiaryphosphine/arsine oxide in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The green compound so formed was filtered, washed thrice with hot absolute ethanol and finally with ether. It was dried under vacuum.

Elemental analysis

Analysis for carbon, hydrogen and phosphorus was obtained from Australian Microanalytical Service Melbourne. Chloride was estimated by Volhard method. In case of arsine oxide complexes, the uranium content was estimated as U₃O₈.

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra (4000-650 cm⁻¹) of the complexes (Table 2) was recorded in nujol on Hilger Watts infrared spectrophotometer.

Reflectance spectra :

Reflectance spectra (2000-250 nm) of the complexes (Table 3) was recorded on Unicam SP700 spectrophotometer.

TABLE I.—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS, COLOUR MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MELTING POINTS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Melting point °C	μ_{eff} B.M.	Percentage of elements found					Percent of elements required				
				C	H	P	Cl	U	C	H	P	Cl	U
UCl ₄ .EPO	Green	>280	1.70	38.31	3.12	7.4	16.8	—	38.51	2.96	7.65	17.50	—
UCl ₄ .BPO	„	175	1.82	39.79	3.51	7.2	17.0	—	40.10	3.30	7.40	16.94	—
UCl ₄ .EAO	„	>280	2.02	35.16	3.12	—	15.8	26.70	34.74	2.67	—	15.81	26.52
UCl ₄ .BAO	„	>280	1.50	36.59	3.27	—	14.9	24.10	36.28	3.02	—	15.33	24.65

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES OF URANIUM (IV) CHLORIDE WITH DITERTIARY PHOSPHINE/ARSINE OXIDES. (cm⁻¹).

Complex	P = O or As = O		P-C _{ar} /As-C _{ar} .	
	Ligand	Complex	Ligand	Complex
UCl ₄ .EPO	1180s	1040s	1115s	1125s
UCl ₄ .BPO	1185s	1040m, 1070s, 1080s	1115s	1125s
UCl ₄ .EAO	880s	835vs	1085s	1085s
UCl ₄ .BAO	880s	830vs, 885w	1085s	1085s

s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, v = very.

TABLE 3—REFLECTANCE SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES OF URANIUM(IV) CHLORIDE WITH DITERTIARYPHOSPHINE AND ARSINE OXIDES

Complex	Position of absorption bands (nm)
UCl ₄ .EPO	400, 435, 475, 525, 570, 620, 645, 665, 745, 865, 945, 1020, 1035, 1155, 1335, 1355, 1540, 1650, 1740, 1890, 1940.
UCl ₄ .BPO	400, 445, 480, 520, 580, 620, 645, 670, 745, 875, 950, 975, 1040, 1110, 1160, 1340, 1345, 1445, 1540, 1635, 1675, 1915, 2035.
UCl ₄ .EAO	440, 565, 580, 645, 745, 845, 1010, 1055, 1135, 1220, 1240, 1370, 1575, 1740, 1840, 1990.
UCl ₄ .BAO	440, 565, 635, 740, 840, 945, 1030, 1135, 1335, 1355, 1435, 1480, 1840.

Magnetic susceptibility :

The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes (Table 1) at room temperature was measured by Gouy method.

Results and Discussions

The elemental analysis of the complexes (Table 1) corresponds to the empirical formula UCl₄.L (where L is EPO, BPO, EAO or BAO). But for UCl₄.BPO, all other complexes do not melt or decompose upto 280°. The general insolubility of these complexes in the common organic solvents precluded the determination of their molecular weights.

Infrared spectra :

The ligands EPO and BPO are characterized by phosphoryl stretch at 1180 and 1185 cm⁻¹ respectively in their infrared spectra. Both of these ligands record P-C_(aromatic) stretch at 1115 cm⁻¹. On complex formation the phosphoryl stretch of EPO is shifted downwards by 140 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination from phosphoryl oxygen. An upward shift of 10 cm⁻¹ in the P-C_(aromatic) stretch also supports the weakening of P = O bond in the complexes due to coordination. In this complex Gans and Smith¹

have also observed the phosphoryl stretch at 1045 cm⁻¹. The infrared spectrum of UCl₄.BPO, however, records three bands assignable to P = O stretch. A medium intensity absorption band appears at 1040 cm⁻¹ and two strong absorption bands appear at 1070 and 1080 cm⁻¹. This splitting of phosphoryl stretching on coordination indicates that complex contains the ligands which are coordinated in a different manner. It may be possible that the ligand acts as a bridge between two uranium (IV) ions. The infrared absorption band at 1040 cm⁻¹ suggests that in the complex the behaviour of BPO is similar to that of EPO. However, the absorption band at 1070 and 1080 cm⁻¹ indicate that the behaviour of BPO is similar to that of Ph₃PO in UCl₄.2Ph₃PO, in which P = O stretch has been observed at 1070 cm⁻¹. the P-C_(aromatic) stretch rises by 10 cm⁻¹ of complex formation.

The arsenyl stretch which in the free ligands EAO and BAO is observed at 880 cm⁻¹ undergoes a fall of 50 cm⁻¹ on coordination with uranium(IV) chloride. This fall is of the same order as that observed in the complexes of uranium(IV) chloride with Ph₃AsO and Et₃AsO^{2,7}. However, in UCl₄.2EAO reported by Selbin and Ortego⁸, the arsenyl stretch has been reported to split into two bands, one at 832 cm⁻¹ and second at 851 cm⁻¹. In the infrared spectra of UCl₄.BAO a very weak intensity band is observed at 885 cm⁻¹. Thus either the ligand is acting as monodentate or coupling of U-O stretch with As = O stretch raises the arsenyl stretch. The comparison of the fall in As = O stretch, in the complexes of uranium(IV) chloride with different ligands indicates that the behaviour of BAO is intermediate between that of Ph₃AsO and Et₃AsO, being more similar to that of the latter. The As-O_(aromatic) stretch in these complexes is not appreciably affected on complex formation which is consistent with the previous observation on the complexes of these ligands with transition metal ions and lanthanide ions^{12,13}. The ligands however, provide two coordination sites, as is evident from the absence of free arsenyl and phosphoryl stretches in the infrared spectra of the complexes.

The absence of water in all the four complexes, coordinated or otherwise is evident from the elemental analysis as well as the infrared spectra.

Reflectance spectra :

In the terminology of Gans and coworkers¹⁴, the reflectance spectra of these complexes corresponds to the "weak" type. Similarly in the reflectance spectra of the complexes shows that in them the metal ion is in similar environments. On the basis of similarity of the spectra of the complexes reported herein to those reported for UCl₄.2Ph₃PO, UCl₄.2Et₃PO, UCl₄.2Ph₃AsO and UCl₄.2Et₃AsO, a hexa coordinated structure with ligands occupying *cis* position in the octahedron is proposed. However, this observation is rather inconsistent to the fact that *cis* and *trans* configuration lead to different electronic spectra¹⁴.

Magnetic susceptibility:

The magnetic susceptibility of these complexes have been measured at 305°K and the values of effective magnetic moments (1.5–2.02 BM) are lower than those reported for uranium(IV) compounds¹⁵. The lower values of magnetic moments suggest that the contribution from the ground state singlet $A_1(^3H_4)$ (diamagnetic) is more than that from the excited state triples $T_1(^3H_4)$. The lower values of magnetic moments are, however, in favour of octahedral environment around uranium(IV).

Though high melting points (except that of $UCl_2 \cdot BPO$) and sparing solubility of these complexes in organic solvents suggest a polymeric nature for these complexes; magnetic susceptibility, extremely low molar conductance in nitrobenzene ($1-2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) and reflectance spectra favour on octahedral stereochemistry for uranium(IV)

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